

Research Article

Unlocking Learning: Implementing Gamification through Escape Room Strategy in a Pre-Diploma Classroom

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Abstract: This teaching innovation introduces a gamification approach named “Find the Code to Escape the Room”, designed for pre-diploma students who often struggle with memory retention and engagement. Gamification applies game-based elements in non-game contexts to create a fun and meaningful learning environment (Deterding et al., 2011). The objective of this innovation is to make the learning more interactive and to support low-achieving students through active, team-based challenges. The core problem addressed is the lack of effectiveness especially for pre-diploma students, who typically have difficulties in understanding and remembering content. Traditional methods do not stimulate their interest or catch their attention. Thus, this innovation uses an escape room-style format that can be used both online and in a manual way. Students solve questions, complete puzzles and find clues related to four main topics in the Introduction to Business course. Each correct answer leads them to the next stage and finally manages to get all the codes. The methodology involves dividing students into teams and assigning game tasks that incorporate the course content. Elements such as time limits, hidden codes, and rewards increase engagement and encourage problem-solving. Findings indicate that students enjoy the activity, demonstrate better understanding of key concepts, and improve their communication and critical thinking skills. This innovation is grounded in constructivist learning theory, emphasizing experience-based knowledge construction. It has potential for commercialization, such as toolkits for educators. Materials are eligible for copyright protection, and initial findings are prepared for publication. In conclusion, “Find the Code to Escape the Room” shows that gamification can transform learning for students below proficiency level and support the development of their essential academic, teamwork and soft skills.

Keywords: gamification; innovation; pre-diploma; escape room.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Gamification is one of the new trends on teaching innovation. The application uses the game method in a non-game context. This innovation project is introduced to the pre-diploma students, who

many of them are struggled with academic performance (especially in English and Mathematic subject) may find that gamification offers an opportunity for them to reengage with learning in a less frightening and more exciting environment. According to Zainuddin et al. (2020), combining game elements into classroom activities can significantly improve student engagement and learning outcomes, especially among lower-performing students. The “Find the Code to Escape the Room” innovation builds upon this concept by combining subject content with problem-solving games that require active participation.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

In pre-diploma education, it is common to see students struggling with low motivation, poor content retention, and difficulty connecting what they have learned to real-world situations. Many of these students come from weaker academic backgrounds (especially English and Mathematics) and have previously found it hard to cope with traditional classroom settings. As a result, they often feel anxious, lack confidence in their abilities, and disengage when learning relies heavily on lectures (Zainuddin et al., 2020).

Traditional methods, like direct instruction, passive notetaking, and memorization, are not going to help them in understanding the topic. Prince (2004) points out that passive learning environments tend to limit how deeply students engage with content, making it even harder for low-performing learners to retain what they have learned. In Malaysia, pre-diploma students face additional hurdles, such as language barriers, weak study skills, and gaps in foundational knowledge, particularly in subjects like business and technology (Khalid et al., 2019).

This situation calls for more engaging, student-centred teaching strategies approaches that not only help students grasp key concepts but also encourage them to participate more actively. One such approach is gamification, which involves using game-like elements such as crosswords puzzle, matching and word search in learning activities to boost motivation and interest (Deterding et al., 2011; Hamari, Koivisto, & Sarsa, 2014). Research shows that gamified learning can enhance engagement, foster intrinsic motivation, and support deeper cognitive processing (Domínguez et al., 2013).

In response to this, the team has designed an innovation project called the “Find the Code to Escape the Room” game. This is a classroom activity that uses the structure of an escape room to deliver course content in a playful but purposeful way. This method gives students the chance to apply what they have learned in a hands-on, collaborative environment. At the same time, it supports the development of key skills like teamwork, decision-making, and problem-solving, making the learning experience more meaningful, enjoyable and effective.

3. METHODOLOGY

The “Find the Code to Escape the Room” activity was designed as a manual, pen-and-paper-based educational escape room tailored to the learning needs of pre-diploma business students. This format was chosen to suit classroom environments where digital access might be limited and to encourage tactile engagement, peer collaboration, and face-to-face interaction, which are vital components of active learning for low-performing learners (Prince, 2004).

Game mechanics were adapted from Nicholson’s RECIPE framework (2015), which highlights key elements of meaningful play in educational escape rooms: Rules, Engagement, Challenge, Interaction, Progression, and Exploration. A strict time limit was enforced (run for 60 minutes), and lecturer acted as game masters, offering minimal guidance and monitoring student behaviour for reflection purposes.

Students were divided into small groups, and each group was assigned a mission consisting of four sequential challenges, each based on a different topic in the syllabus. Rather than rotating through physical stations, each group received all four tasks upfront in a printed envelope pack. These tasks were carefully designed to encourage critical thinking, reinforce conceptual understanding, and build engagement through gamified elements.

In the first challenge, students explored the topic of Introduction to Business. They were given a brief scenario-based question that required basic business knowledge, followed by a crossword puzzle where the clues were embedded in the initial scenario. The objective was to reinforce fundamental terminology and definitions in a playful yet cognitively engaging way (Fotaris & Mastoras, 2019).

The second task focused on the Forms of Business Ownership. Students answered a series of short questions and then searched for the correct terms in a word search puzzle. This format encouraged familiarity with legal and structural aspects of business types, which can often be memorization-heavy for pre-diploma learners. The gamified format helped reduce cognitive overload by segmenting information and embedding it in a retrieval-based activity (Hamari et al., 2014).

The third activity covered Basic Management Concepts. Here, students were given a matching activity where they had to correctly align questions with a pool of pre-written answers, such as matching managerial roles to appropriate functions. This task promoted categorization and reasoning, which are key cognitive skills in management education (Böheim et al., 2022).

The final challenge was based on Entrepreneurship and business branding. Students were shown a series of cropped or partial business logos and had to correctly identify the company name. This task tested their visual memory and real-world brand awareness, enhancing their ability to connect theoretical concepts with familiar business entities, a practice known to strengthen long-term retention (Nicholson, 2015).

For each topic, students will have to answer the clue questions that contained the code for the escape room. Once the group can answer all questions correctly and manage to complete the game puzzle, they then present the code to the lecturer. The group with the correct final code is declared the winner. This gamification is like the real escape room dynamics, using progressive challenges, time constraints, and goal-oriented gameplay, while anchoring learning in course-specific outcomes (Clarke et al., 2017).

Debriefing session was conducted to guide students in discussing what strategies were most effective, what concepts were reinforced, and how they collaborated to complete tasks. Other than that, constructive feedback was collected during this debrief session. It is crucial for reinforcing learning, as research shows that reflection turns activity into deeper understanding (Clarke et al., 2017). Observations and student feedback were documented as qualitative evidence of engagement and learning progression.

4. FINDINGS

From early observations and students' feedback, it was clear that the escape room activity had a strong impact. Students seemed more engaged, remembered the content better, and showed increased motivation. The combination of learning and game playing encouraged them to take a more active role in their understanding of the subject. Several students shared that the gamification approach helped them understand the subject in a new way, making it easier to recall important concepts afterward (Fotaris & Mastoras, 2019; Subhash & Cudney, 2018).

To better understand their experiences, students were asked to submit short video reflections after the activity. These clips offered valuable insight, not just into what they have learned, but how they felt during the process. Many described it as “fun but challenging,” and mentioned that the hands-on puzzles was rather difficult. The energy in the room was noticeably higher, and the friendly competition seemed to sharpen their focus.

Beyond academic content, the activity also helped students build important soft skills like communication, leadership, and teamwork. Working in small groups, they naturally took on different roles, discussed possible answers, and encouraged each other, especially under time pressure. These skills, highlighted by Trilling and Fadel (2009) as essential for the 21st century, are also key priorities in higher education (Anderson et al., 2018). During the debrief, many students were more willing to speak up and explain their reasoning, showing growth in confidence and critical thinking.

5. DISCUSSION

This innovation is consistent with constructivist learning theory, which posits that learners actively build knowledge through experience and social interaction (Vygotsky, 1978). Students must focus on answering questions, solving problems and applying what they have learned in order to find the hidden code. Students will have to discuss and communicate with their group members to find the code. In the end, they may successfully complete collecting all the code thus manage to escape the room.

This activity also drew on key ideas from game-based learning, which can make lessons more effective by helping students feel more emotionally connected, stay focused on their goals, and feel motivated from within (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Subhash & Cudney, 2018). By adding elements like time limits, hidden clues, and step-by-step puzzles, the activity closely resembled real escape room experiences. This type of challenge-based gameplay has been shown to boost student engagement and support deeper understanding of the material (Fotaris & Mastoras, 2019).

The use of a manual, paper-based escape room such as crosswords, word searches, and matching activities, was especially helpful for pre-diploma students who may not be comfortable with digital tools or who do not have regular access to technology. This approach supports Prince’s (2004) view that active learning methods should be tailored to students’ backgrounds and available resources. However, this method was also used to challenge student’s memorization and understanding skills.

In addition, asking students to share short video reflections after the activity helped capture their thoughts and feelings about the experience. This not only offered valuable insight into their learning process but also supported the emotional side of learning. It reflects current practices in reflective teaching, where student feedback plays a key role in understanding both what they have learned and felt during the lesson (Moon, 2004).

6. CONCLUSION

This gamification activity is suitable for the pre-diploma student to display their knowledge and understanding about the course. This can also improve their learning experiences and improve their intelligence and learning skills. The gamification method tasks were done in a such that it integrated the questions with the syllabus requirement. Students can understand the theoretical contents as well as enhancing their teamwork, communication and leadership skills.

The reflection videos from students talking about their experiences post activity helped the lecturer to better understand students’ feelings and their thought on the game. Reflection will help

students to look back at what they have learned throughout the game. The simplicity of the activity could be used in other classes as well especially if technology is not in place.

This innovation holds potential for further academic publication, commercialization as a teaching kit or training module, and intellectual property registration as a branded pedagogical tool. Future iterations may explore longitudinal studies or compare student performance across gamified and traditional formats to deepen the evidence base.

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